

**MODERN WAYS OF TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE IN THE FIELD OF
MEDICINE**

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Abstract

This article is devoted to analyze the effective and innovative and also quite interesting ways of teaching foreign language, that is, have a great importance of IT in the learning process as well as in the process of raising motivation among students to a higher level. It also describes different methods of multimedia among which the outline of video lessons, role-playing a game lessons, project based-learning have the leading role.

Key words: teaching methods, foreign language learning, effective methods, power point presentation, educational process, and information technology.

Аннотация

Эта статья посвящена анализу эффективных и инновационных, а также довольно интересных способов обучения иностранному языку, то есть имеет большое значение ИТ в учебном процессе, а также в процессе повышения мотивации, учащихся на более высокий уровень. В нем также

описаны различные методы мультимедиа, среди которых основная часть видеоархивов, ролевых игры, уроков игры, основанных на проектах.

Ключевые слова: методы обучения, изучение иностранных языков, эффективные методы, презентация Power Point, учебный процесс, информационные технологии

English, the official language of the entire world, is a very difficult language to teach and learn as well for some students who are not in the field of linguistics. In fact, each language differs from teaching. We know that, present time information technologies stand out as a requirement, and burst into all spheres of our life rapidly. Using of new technologies into the educational process is always considered a progressive way that promoted motivation of learning. It is so crucial to raise the level of knowledge of students by means of bringing in newest information technologies including multimedia assets as well.

At the present time communication technologies become a normal for most of the higher educational establishments in the whole world. Multimedia technologies can be described as package of video, audio and other means of reflecting information that is united in an interactive software environment. Multimedia means permit to include almost all five sense of students, combining the printed text, graphic image, movable video, static photos and audio-record. Because of using multimedia means, students can learn all aspects of language perfectly, such as, phonetic, grammatical, lexical and communicative, that allows more effective and quicker mastering of language material, language skills and abilities. The implementation of new methods of learning that provide the development of communicative, creative and professional competences and stimulate the requirement of future specialist in self-education based on the content and management of educational process is required from modern educational establishment nowadays.

The aim of learning foreign language in the higher educational establishment is forming professional communicative competence among students with the help of development and perfection of all types of language activity: reading, speaking, writing, and listening and lexical-grammar.

As practice shows, a computer, from all the existent means of study, is the best choice to be implemented into the structure of educational process. A computer is capable to provide all round control of educational process as well. Computer also created a lot of possibilities for organization of self-assessment work of students at a lesson of foreign language. Students can use a computer both for the study themes and for self-control of gained knowledge.

One of the most successful examples of means of learning is learning by Power Point Presentation.

Foreign language presentation is a way of showing the creative, newly made and adapted for the certain level of Students language information.

Multimedia presentation is based on the use of audiovisual possibilities of computer technologies. There is a general algorithm of multimedia presentation.

Accordingly, it is very important for teacher to follow such steps:

- To define pedagogical tasks which are going to be solved by means of created multimedia presentation;
- To think over the aim and tasks of the slides creation;
- Taking into account the Students' potential possibilities;
- To write down the script of multimedia presentation;
- To create the structure of multimedia presentation;
- To apply animation and voice effects.

Power Point Presentation is used in educational establishment of different levels an specific such as:

- Objects of study in a course of information and communication technologies;
- Means of electronic and paper support in the process of educational orientation and explanation the material by the teacher and also are used to exchange education experience.

Video. Video plays an important role in the study of a foreign language. It helps to create dynamic visualization that makes a lesson more interesting. However, ordinary watching of films will give no effects.

The understanding of content and language means used in a film after viewing it, spare the special attention to translation of content.

Project based-learning. In the modern world, literacy consist of a number of skills (express your own opinion, wishes, and necessities orally; to read and write; to find and to choose necessary information). The evaluation of knowledge and abilities is the process of learning, not the outcome; the educational process is

not preparation for life, for this reason participating in bit must bring pleasure. One of such interesting forms of studies is non-traditional lesson of foreign language. Such lessons impress by their variety: lesson excursion, business games, lessons dialogues, lessons press conferences, etc. The methods of projects plays crucial role in the improvement of mastering of foreign language and in the development of motivation among students.

Role-playing based learning. Role-playing is mostly used when it is needed to analyze a problem and find the best solution. The practice can be tried in different fields like teaching language. It should be pointed out that, the ability of a teacher to use IT in the educational process became one of the substantial parts of the professional competence. It is a well-known fact that learning is more effective and faster when the tasks themselves arouse interest and curiosity in the student. So Jeremy Harmer, a renowned British author of textbooks for learning English, highlights several advantages of using ROLE in the lesson:

- Role-playing game is fun and helps to increase the student's motivation to assimilate new information;

- Quiet and shy students have the opportunity to more openly express their own opinions;

So, role play is a task aimed at developing speaking skills. What`s more, role play topics usually depend on the lexical and grammatical material that is being studied at the moment.

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